

**IN THE COURT OF COMMON PLEAS
FRANKLIN COUNTY, OHIO**

<p>ABSOLUTE RESOLUTIONS INVESTMENTS, LLC 8000 Norman Center Drive Suite 115 Bloomington, MN 55437 PLAINTIFF</p> <p style="text-align: center;">v.</p> <p>KEANA BAUTISTA 2004 Starbridge Court Columbus, OH 43235 DEFENDANT</p>	<p>CASE NUMBER 2024CV009713</p> <p>[Transferred from Municipal Court Case Number 2024CVF017156]</p> <p>JUDGE: Hon. Andy Miller</p> <p>DEFENDANT'S MOTION FOR ORDER TO SHOW CAUSE WHY PLAINTIFF SHOULD NOT BE HELD IN CONTEMPT FOR FABRICATING EVIDENCE AND MEMORANDUM SUPPORTING DEFENDANT'S MOTION</p>
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**DEFENDANT'S MOTION FOR ORDER TO SHOW CAUSE
WHY PLAINTIFF SHOULD NOT BE HELD IN CONTEMPT
FOR FABRICATING EVIDENCE
AND MEMORANDUM SUPPORTING DEFENDANT'S MOTION**

COMES NOW Defendant Keana Bautista (hereinafter, "Bautista") and files Defendant's Motion for Order to Show Cause Why Plaintiff Should Not Be Held in Contempt for Fabricating Evidence (hereinafter, "Motion") and Memorandum Supporting Defendant's Motion (hereinafter, "Memorandum"), showing this Honorable Court as follows:

I. INTRODUCTION

Plaintiff has the audacity to cut-and-paste a fabricated date onto an old affidavit and certify under oath that it was subscribed and sworn before a notary. As shown here, every pixel of the **2025-Aug-11** signature overlaps perfectly with every pixel of the **2025-Sep-08** signature:

Absolute Resolutions Investments, LLC (hereinafter, "ARI") and its counsel would have this Honorable Court believe that the affiant signed both documents perfectly, in exactly the same way (including alignment with the signature line), a month apart from each other.

Depending on whether ARI or its counsel is responsible for this **forgery**, this Honorable Court should impose the harshest of sanctions.

II. FACTS

A. *Signature Line of Affidavit Executed on 2025-Aug-11*

On 2025-Aug-11, ARI's counsel filed with this Honorable Court a document having the title "Plaintiff's Affidavit" (hereinafter, "August Affidavit") by Tiasha Broback (hereinafter, "Broback"), under penalty of perjury, with the following signature line (hereinafter, "**August Image**"):

A rectangular box containing a handwritten signature line. The text "Dated:" is printed in black, followed by the date "8/11/2025" written in blue ink. Below the date is a horizontal line. Underneath this line is a cursive signature in blue ink that appears to read "Tiasha Broback".

Although the August Affidavit was allegedly signed by Broback, the August Affidavit was not notarized.

B. *Signature Line of Affidavit Executed on 2025-Sep-08*

Approximately a month later, on 2025-Sep-08, ARI's counsel filed with this Honorable Court another affidavit by Broback (hereinafter, "September Affidavit"), again under penalty of perjury. The substance of the September Affidavit was identical to the substance of the August Affidavit. However, unlike the August Affidavit, the September Affidavit was allegedly

¹ Affidavit of Sam Han, Ph.D. (hereinafter, "Han Affidavit"), attached hereto as an Exhibit, at ¶ 14.

notarized by Audrey Anne Fermanich (hereinafter, "Fermanich"). Importantly, the September Affidavit expressly recited that it was "[s]ubscribed and sworn before [Fermanich] on "9/8/2025" and included an alleged signature and notarial stamp for Fermanich.

The following affiant signature line (hereinafter, "**September Image**") appeared in the September Affidavit:

C. Overlay Comparison Between the August Image and the September Image

An overlay of the **September Image** and **August Image** demonstrated that there was a perfect overlap in the signatures, as follows:

In other words, the signature from 2025-Aug-11 was a perfect overlapping match to the signature from 2025-Sep-08, meaning that every pixel in the signature of the **August Image** overlapped

² Han Affidavit, ¶ 16.

³ Han Affidavit, ¶ 23.

perfectly with every pixel in the signature of the **September Image**.⁴

Indeed, a side-by-side comparison of the signatures demonstrates that every stroke of the pen is identical, the placement of the signature above the signature line is identical, the placement of the date line is identical, etc., as follows:

Additionally, remnants of forward slash marks ("/") that separate month, day, and year from the date line in the **August Image** appeared in exactly the same place in the **September Image**, as follows (shown with boxes and arrows and at the tops of the images):

Additionally, the underlined portion of "9/8/2025" is blocked by the allegedly hand-written date "9/8/2025" as if the hand-written date "9/8/2025" was cut and then pasted onto the page after "Dated" (thereby covering or effectively deleting a portion of the underlining).⁶

In other words, the date in the September Affidavit was a **cut-and-paste forgery**, with the signature being the one that was executed in 2025-Aug-11 (not 2025-Sep-08), being identical in each stroke of the pen, being identical in placement over the signature line, and being so identical in every aspect that it would be a mathematical impossibility.⁷

D. The September Affidavit Is a Clear Forgery

Clearly, the September Affidavit is a forgery.

⁴ Han Affidavit, ¶ 25.

⁵ Han Affidavit, ¶ 24.

⁶ Han Affidavit, ¶ 25.

⁷ Han Affidavit, ¶ 25.

In view of the compelling evidence of fraud on this Honorable Court, Bautista now files this Motion, requesting an expedited hearing for ARI and its counsel to show cause why the harshest of sanctions should not be imposed for such a flagrant fabrication of evidence.

III. ARGUMENT

Bautista's argument is simple and clear: ARI and its counsel should not be permitted to defile this Honorable Court by filing forgeries and then committing perjury about those forgeries. See, O.R.C. § 2913.31(A)(2) (defining the offense of forgery).

Here, the evidence is compelling that the September Affidavit was not executed under oath before a notary on 2025-Sep-08. Rather, the evidence clearly shows that the signature line on the September Affidavit was actually executed a month before and not in the presence of a notary.

Because this forgery constitutes a serious offense against this Honorable Court, Bautista respectfully moves for an expedited hearing for ARI and its counsel to show cause why it should not be held in contempt.

IV. REQUESTED RELIEF IF FABRICATION OF EVIDENCE IS PROVEN

If this Honorable Court should determine that the September Affidavit is a wholly manufactured document that was accompanied by perjurious statements under oath, then Bautista respectfully moves for the harshest of sanctions, including but not limited to:

- (a) striking ARI's pleadings in this action;
- (b) entering a default judgment against ARI in this action;
- (c) awarding to Bautista all fees, costs, and expenses associated with this action;
- (d) requiring ARI to immediately withdraw, dismiss, or move to suspend any cases in which documents have been executed by either Fermanich or Brobak;
- (e) advising all courts in which ARI has had cases pending of the forgery from this case; and
- (f) requiring ARI's counsel to review and produce the originals (not copies) of all signed documents for every pending case in Ohio in which either Fermanich or Brobak are

signatories.

Because of the gravity of the contempt shown to the administration of justice, and because the forgery now brings into doubt any document that has been allegedly executed by Broback or Fermanich, Bautista respectfully submits that the requested relief is reasonably proportional to the offense committed.

V. CONCLUSION

Bautista respectfully moves for a hearing to require ARI and its counsel to show cause why the harshest of sanctions should not be imposed for submitting forgeries with this Honorable Court and committing perjury about those forgeries.

[SIGNATURE TO FOLLOW]

Respectfully submitted on 2025-Sep-09.

/s/ Andrew Barnes
Andrew Barnes (0098065)
A Barnes Law, LLC
90 Rhoades Center Dr
Centerville, Ohio 45458
Telephone: (513) 494-6616
Barnes@abarneslaw.com
Attorney for Defendant

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ABSOLUTE RESOLUTIONS INVESTMENTS, LLC 8000 Norman Center Drive Suite 115 Bloomington, MN 55437 PLAINTIFF v. KEANA BAUTISTA 2004 Starbridge Court Columbus, OH 43235 DEFENDANT	CASE NUMBER 2024CV009713 [Transferred from Municipal Court Case Number 2024CVF017156] JUDGE: Hon. Andy Miller CERTIFICATE OF FILING AND SERVICE
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CERTIFICATE OF FILING AND SERVICE

The undersigned counsel certifies that the above-attached Defendant's Motion for Order to Show Cause Why Plaintiff Should Not Be Held in Contempt for Fabricating Evidence (hereinafter, "Motion") and Memorandum Supporting Defendant's Motion (hereinafter, "Memorandum") was filed using this Honorable Court's Case Management / Electronic Case Filing ("CM/ECF") system on the date set forth herein, which will serve electronically a Notice of Electronic Filing ("NEF") on all counsel of record in this matter, all of whom have consented to accepting the NEF as electronic service through the Court's CM/ECF. Out of an abundance of caution, this filing was also served by email to all counsel of record in this matter.

[SIGNATURE TO FOLLOW]

Respectfully submitted on 2025-Sep-09.

/s/ Andrew Barnes
Andrew Barnes (0098065)
A Barnes Law, LLC
90 Rhoades Center Dr
Centerville, Ohio 45458
Telephone: (513) 494-6616
Barnes@abarneslaw.com
Attorney for Defendant

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AFFIDAVIT OF SAM HAN, PH.D.

I, Sam Han, declare as follows:

1. I am over the age of eighteen years and I am competent to make all of the statements in this Affidavit.
2. I voluntarily give the statements in this Affidavit in support of Defendant Keana Bautista (hereafter, "Bautista") in the above-captioned proceeding.
3. I do not represent Bautista as legal counsel.
4. I have never made an appearance as legal counsel on behalf of Bautista.
5. All statements made herein come from personal knowledge unless expressly stated otherwise.
6. I declare under penalty of perjury under the laws of the United States of America that the statements that are contained in this Affidavit are true and correct.
7. I studied Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (hereinafter, "EECS") at the University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Michigan.
8. Upon completing my course requirements in EECS, I was awarded a Bachelor of Science in Electrical Engineering.
9. I also obtained my master's degree (M.E.) and doctoral degree (Ph.D.) from the Biomedical Engineering Department at Worcester Polytechnic Institute, Worcester,

Massachusetts.

10. For my Ph.D., I worked with sophisticated imaging systems while conducting research on strokes and tumors.

11. Thus, I have personal knowledge of digital images and digital image processing techniques.

12. I have also taught statistics for several years.

13. I was asked to examine a digital image of a signature that was allegedly signed on 2025-Aug-11 (hereinafter, "**August Image**").

14. I personally observed that the **August Image** appears as follows:

Dated: 8/11/2025

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read "J. B. B.", is written above a horizontal line.

15. I was also asked to examine a digital image of a signature that was allegedly signed on 2025-Sep-08 (hereinafter, "**September Image**").

16. I personally observed that the **September Image** appears as follows:

Dated. 9/8/2025

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "J. B. B.", is written above a horizontal line.

17. I was also asked to compare the **August Image** with the **September Image**.

18. To compare the **August Image** with the **September Image**, I first made sure that the **August Image** and the **September Image** were scaled to the same size.

19. In scaling the images for comparison, I made sure that the proportions were not altered for either image (meaning, the height-to-width of the images remained exactly the same as they appeared in the original).

20. This allowed me to compare the two (2) digital images fairly.

21. Next, I digitally overlaid the **August Image** onto the **September Image** and adjusted the transparency of the **August Image** so that both images could be compared visually.

22. The digital overlay technique that I applied is the computer imaging equivalent of holding up two (2) pieces of paper to the light to compare printed copies.

23. The digital overlay (showing the **August Image** atop the **September Image**) is shown here (hereinafter, "**Overlay Image**"):

Dated: 8/18/2008

J. B. B.

24. In the **Overlay Image**:

- the images of the numbers on the dates do not coincide perfectly;
- the forward slash marks ("/") that separate month, day, and year do not coincide perfectly, but the two (2) remnants of the "/" at the top of the **September Image** coincides perfectly with the top of the "/" in the **August Image**, as shown here (side-by-side, with boxes and arrows showing the overlap at the top of the "/"):

- the underlined portion of "9/8/2025" is blocked by "9/8/2025" as if "9/8/2025" has been cut-and-pasted onto the page after "Dated" (thereby covering or effectively deleting a portion of the underlining); and

- the images of the signatures overlap perfectly, as shown here:

25. The mathematical probability of every pixel in the signature of the **August Image** overlapping perfectly with every pixel in the signature of the **September Image** is a statistical impossibility.

26. Attached hereto as an Exhibit are true and accurate enlargements of the **August Image**, the **September Image**, and the **Overlay Image**.

FURTHER AFFIANT SAYETH NAUGHT.

[SIGNATURE TO FOLLOW]

Executed on 2025-SEPTEMBER-09, in Dayton, Ohio.

Sam Han

STATE OF OHIO, ||
MONTGOMERY COUNTY || SS:

Sworn to before me and signed in my presence this 9th day of September, 2025.

Brian Sullivan, Notary Public
Montgomery County, Ohio
My commission expires NEVER

BRIAN P. SULLIVAN, Attorney at Law
Notary Public, State of Ohio
My Commission has no expiration date.
Section 147.03 O. R. C.

Dated: 8/11/2025

Dated. 9/8/2025

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OVERLAY OF 2025-AUG-11 SIGNATURE ONTO 2025-SEP-08 SIGNATURE

Dated: 8/18/2025

Li B. B. B.

Dated: 8/11/2025

